

DID WE KILL JOHN LENNON?

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ABSTRACT

Did We Kill John Lennon? **Introduction:** Mark David Chapman shot and killed John Lennon, outside his apartment building, the Dakota, in New York City on December 8, 1980. Chapman remained at the scene, reading "The Catcher in the Rye", until police arrived. Since Lennon's death allegations that he had been killed because of his opposition to the Vietnam War have emerged. Objective To determine whether John Lennon was a victim of Government Engineered Assassination (GEA). **Method:** We have reviewed publicly available data on John Lennon's death: Wikipedia., Encyclopedia Britannica, Potash P./ "Drugs as weapons against us, "The US vs. John Lennon, the documentary, Weiner A /" Gimme Some Truth, Bressler F., Who killed John Lennon ?" Strongman F/John Lennon" Whelan D./Mind Games: The Assassination of John Lennon and applied the probability theory to projects odds of certainty that" John Lennon was a victim of GEA". **Results:** 18 observations consistent with the hypothesis John Lennon was a victim of GEA and inconsistent with the null hypothesis. The odds of this projection to be accurate is %99.999. **Discussion:** Evidence of persecution by the US intelligent agencies, signature traits of GEA and coverup, supported by mathematical projections suggest John Lennon was a victim of GEA. **Conclusion:** John Lennon was a victim of GEA.

KEYWORDS: The odds of this projection to be accurate is %99.999.

Did We Kill John Lennon?

Mark David Chapman shot and killed John Lennon, outside his apartment building, the Dakota, in New York City on December 8, 1980. Lennon was returning from a recording session with his wife, Yoko Ono, when Chapman fired five shots, four of which hit Lennon. Chapman remained at the scene, reading The Catcher in the Rye, until police arrived.

Confidential declassified FBI Files contained facsimiles of the documents, including "lengthy reports by confidential informants detailing the daily lives of anti-war activists, memos to the White House, transcripts of TV shows on which Lennon appeared. The files also revealed that *Hoover proposed that Lennon be arrested by local police on drug charges.*

Multiple scholarly publications() offered circumstantial evidence that John Lennon was killed by US intelligence agencies to prevent him influencing people.

OBJECTIVE

To determine whether John Lennon was a victim of Government engineered assassination (GEA).

METHOD: METHOD

We have reviewed publicly available data on John Lennon's death: Wikipedia., Encyclopedia Britannica, Potash P./ "Drugs as weapons against us , "The US vs. John Lennon, the documentary, Weiner A /" Gimme Some Truth, Bressler F., Who killed John Lennon ?" Strongman F/John Lennon" Whelan D./Mind Games :The Assassination of John.

Lennon and applied the probability theory to projects odds of certainty that" John Lennon was a victim of GEA". The probability of a physically possible observation to be correct exponentially increases by each supporting evidence and can be expressed as an equation $R = 1/2^x$. R representing the probability of random occurrence and x the number of diverse evidence consistent with the hypothesis and inconsistent with the

null hypothesis This equation is based upon the premise that each supporting evidence is a hypothesis, a logical inference from observing facts from which consequences may be deduced with a 50% chance of being correct, and therefore the final outcome would be the same as the probability of random occurrence in flipping a coin. Hence it would be like heads coming up at consecutive times. For instance, the probability of random occurrence of heads coming up 10 consecutive times is $\frac{1}{2}^{10} = 1/1024 = 0.0009 = 0.09\%$ Of significance, consistent with the framework of flipping a coin, potential flaws of statistical analysis, randomness and buys have no effect on the accuracy of final outcome. As long as it is fair play without tricks, it does not matter who flips the coin.

RESULTS

18 observations consistent with "John Lennon was a victim of government engineered assassination" and inconsistent with "he was not".^[1-7]

1. Murder by a patsy /lone lunatic/anti social person consistent with a murder by a programmed killer.^[1,2]
 2. Behavior consistent with actions of a programmed killer; did not run, calmly read "Catcher in the Rye."^[1,2,3]
 3. CIA listed Lennon as a threat to National security.^[4]
 4. FBI surveillance: Hoover proposed that Lennon be arrested by local police on drug charges".^[1,2,3,4]
 5. Phil Strongman author of John Lennon believed Mark Chapman was a CIA hypnotized killer.^[1,2,3,4]
 6. John Mark, former CIA agent believed Mark Chapman was a CIA hypnotized killer.^[1,2,3,4]
 7. Attorney Daniel Sheehan of Christie Institute believed Mark Chapman was a CIA hypnotized killer.^[1,2,3]
 8. Lieutenant Arthur O'Conner believed Mark Chapman was a CIA hypnotized killer.^[1,2,3,4]
 9. CIA's MKULTRA project trained programmed assassins and Chapman received treatment at CASTLE MEMORIAL -a CIA training place-.^[5,6]...
 10. Chapman worked at CASTLE MEMORIA for 27 months.^[5,6]
 11. Chapman worked at YMCA (a CIA friendly organization).
 12. Lennon publicized his objections to the Vietnam war JFK, RFK, MLK and other opponents to the war were killed.^[5,6]
 13. Lost records YMCA consistent with a cover up.^[1,2,3]
 14. Lost Records at NYDA consistent with a cover up.^[1,2,3]
 15. Altered travel records consistent with a cover up.^[1,2,3]
 16. Overseas travels inconsistent with Chapman's income.^[1,2,3]
 17. Jose Vjosequn Sanjen Pardono: The doorman at Dakota, a CIA asset brigade Bay of Pigs.^[1,2,3,4]
 18. Chapman's bizarre behavior at the crime scene was not investigated to determine intoxication.^[1,2,3]
- 18 observations consistent with the hypothesis John Lennon was a victim of GEA and inconsistent with the

null hypothesis suggest John Lennon was a victim of GEA. The chances of this conclusion being correct is % 99.999.

DISCUSSION

Evidence of persecution by the US intelligent agencies, signature traits of GEA and coverup, supported by mathematical projections suggest John Lennon was a victim of GEA.

CONCLUSION

John Lennon was a victim of GEA.

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